

DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN CULTURAL COOPERATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Cultural development process of Karakalpakstan museums to the recognition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the whole world is in qyshmok. These institutions began to pay even more attention to the national and artistic works of the Karakalpak people. In the museums of the Republic of Karakalpakstan there are exhibits that reveal the history of Karakalpakstan, the history of cultural and historical monuments, as well as show the traditional culture and art of the Karakalpak people. Among them I.V.Museum of Karakalpak State Art named after Savisky, State Museum of history and culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Museum of Archeology of Ellikkala District, Museum of ecology of Muynak District, Museum of the 90s of Qanlikul District, Museum of Berdak at Karakalpak State University, "a.Shamuratova " are home museums [1.3 B.]. Various unique collectibles stored in museum funds can be listed. They, in turn, are becoming more important in attracting the attention of tourists.

Republic Of Karakalpakstan I.V.The Savisky State Museum of art, which has the best collection of works of art on the territory of Asia, ranks second in terms of the number and importance of avant-garde paintings in the World[2. 7].

The museum attracted the attention of the World Press with its unique collection, and for many art fans, the Nukus museum became a "cultural traveler" [3]. in his opinion, the English newspaper in the World Press "The Hidden Secrets of Savisky" in "Gardian"[4], s.Kinzer's "sa'nat in the desert "in the New York Times[5], DJ.Page"avant-garde Oasis" [6] in his articles, experts recognized tomny.

The museum exhibits contribute to the development of the tourism sector in the Republic and the economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan[7].

Karakalpakstan, as some tour operators say, is the most remote part of Uzbekistan, which attracts tourists only by the Savisky Museum and the tragic history of the Aral Sea. Considered the most ancient caravan routes of Karakalpakstan, the YLL connecting the East with the West through the famous Silk Road, the ancient and medieval civilisation contributed to the emergence of highly original sources and excellent examples of spiritual culture. There are thousands of historical monuments and ancient monuments on the territory of the Republic, many of which are historically and archeological.

On the basis of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated December 2, 2016 PF-4861[9] on the basis of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan " on measures to ensure the Among them are Navruz, Melon Festival, Melon Festival, Zorat holiday, horses and folk games, folk songs and musical competitions, Bakhshi, recitation holidays. All events are carried out together with fairs where local craftsmen can buy souvenirs. Insufficient ignorance of tour

operators, the lack of a strong connection between them and the influence of cultural institutions and non-governmental organizations of the flow of foreign tourists to the country indicate a negative impact on the development of Tourism. To see many unique historical, scientific, artistic and cultural objects in the territory of the Republic, among them are the route of Sayohat tourism: Khujayli district Mizdakhkan archaeological complex, Kunkhut OTA shrine of Kunchuzha District, Sultan Uvays Bobo shrine of Beruniy district, Hakim OTA tomb of Muynak district, Sheikh Jalil Bobo mausoleum of Amudarya district, Norinjan Bobo tomb of Ellikkala District, Kunkhoja and Berdaq poets tombs in Chimboy district; Ecological tourism route: Muynak district Aral Sea, Sudoche Lake, sheep Amu Darya Biosphere Reserve, Kunningot district Ustyurt plain, Borsakelmes Salt Lake (salt mine), open sky ships cemetery, Urga village; to the architectural tourism route: Chilpiq, Ayazgala, Tuproqqala, Gyaur Castle, Djampiq Castle, Iyshan Castle, Red Castle, Kat Castle, Jambas Castle archaeological objects and many others. includes objects close to 10]. Of these, 131 are archaeological objects, 24 architectural objects, 91 monumental objects and 45 attractions[11].

In the field of tourism, a steady increase in the direction of the East is widely observed. He noted that the number of people who want to visit Karakalpakstan is increasing. The countries of Central Asia are united on the basis of a single "Great Silk Road" chain, which includes about 20 countries, including the road extending from Japan to Europe. The main importance on this path was occupied by Uzbekistan, which is famous for its domes. Karakalpakstan has a fund of additional natural objects necessary for tourism. These include the landscapes of the Ustyurt plateau, the Kyzylkum deserts, the amudarya tributaries and the Valley.

Located in the Beruni region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Holy traveler Baday-Tukai can be used as a tourist object. Having its own not very large area, travelgox is very rich in fauna and flora.

There is a monument "angry Forest" on the Goycha Hill of the Fourkul region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which is not known to many who belong to the Stone Age. It is possible that it will become one of the most interesting objects for all in the development of Tourism.

Director of the Institute of history of the Karakalpakstan branch of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan member of the New York Academy of Sciences V.N.Yagodin added his Hissa to develop tourism in Karakalpakstan. A number of projects were developed within the framework of the "Golden Ring of ancient Khorezm" in cooperation with the Institute of history, archeology and Ethnography of the Karakalpakstan Department of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Institute of restoration (restoration) of the city of Tashkent. A large number of historical sites have been preserved in good condition, despite the fact that there are several millennia before the appearance of historical luminaries[12].

In the II-IV centuries, Tuproqala was the seat of the Khorezm rulers. As a result of excavations in this city, a number of important archaeological settlements were found and included among those recognized in the world. From the sentence "Palace of Kings", "Palace of the Garatanites", "Palace of dancers", "Palace of victory". Also here are preserved monuments of ancient culture: frescoes, clay huts, samples of Lake labor.

Development of international joint work of cultural and historical heritage in Karakalpakstan and yrganish byyicha one of the unique archaeological objects of Uzbekistan Republic is the ancient and medieval settlement of Mizdakhkan, located 3 km from its master. Mizdakhkan is the third largest city in terms of the size of the medieval Khorezm state, and it was considered

one of the Centers of the dekhkan castles. Archaeological monuments, vessels, coins and other items found there signal that extensive trade relations were established through the Great Silk Road of Mizdahkan.

The Great Silk Road Caravan service network found on the Ustyurt plateau is one of the most notable within archaeological finds. The caravan Palace, wells and other structures have been preserved in good condition in the sandy deserts. In such ancient monuments as daukesken makhbara, Beleuli caravan Palace, Kargancha town, water-collecting structures were created using an ancient method of irrigation of lands. And through it it can be seen that the population living in Usturt has a high potential. The road through the territory of Karakalpakstan became an integral part of the Great Silk Road[13]. It is also necessary to use certain environmental features in the development of tourism in the Republic. In Karakalpakstan, a project for the development of tourism was developed in cooperation with the media, historian scientists and museum staff. In the south-western part of the capital of Karakalpakstan, a modern avtolager (autocamping) was built. Every day, autotourists from Kazakhstan, Russia, Turkmenistan and the Bribaltika countries visit there.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh. Paragraph 8 of the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 17, 2017"on the program of measures to further improve the conditions and the level of population tourism of the Republic of Karakalpakstan "in the period of Mirziyoyev's visit to the Republic of Karakalpakstan, muvafiq," burakhan OTA "in the District of Kungradot in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan," Hakim OTA "aqimbet Bakshi", "oppressed suluv" in khujayli District, The tasks of the restoration of cultural heritage sites and improvement of their surroundings were determined.

In accordance with this decision, funds were allocated and re-completed to the Tomb of Akimbet Bakhshi in Chimboy district, the Tomb of Mazlumhan suluv and Shamun Nabi in the Mizdakhkan complex in Khujayli district, the Tomb of Akimbet Bakshi. Repair work was carried out by allocating 102.0 million soums to the Tomb of mazlumhan Suluv, and 370.0 million soums to the Tomb of Shamun Nabi[14].

Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2018 No. 5326 "on additional organizational measures to create favorable conditions for the development of the tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[15], in accordance with the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2018 No. 3514 "on measures to ensure the rapid development of domestic tourism"[16] A total of 211,478 people, of which 48,745 Uzbek, 13,319 foreign tourists, 68,980 young people, 80,434 visited museums for free in order to implement the "travel around Uzbekistan" project. In order to promote the museum's exhibits, employees of state museums were provided with 43 articles in newspapers and magazines, information about the activities of museums in 202 TV shows and radio broadcasts through the media.

In Karakalpakstan, there is an opportunity to attract the attention of tourists not only by the Savisky Museum and the tragic history of the Aral Sea, but also by the ancient caravan routes of the region, high samples of ancient and medieval civilisation, thousands of historical monuments and ancient monuments on the territory of the Republic.

The development of ecological tourism in Karakalpakstan has also become an important component of the program for the further development of Tourism. To attract ecotourism lovers through a unique landscape of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in order to create an

ecotourism infrastructure in the Akcha Kul area of Ellikkala district, to develop new ecotourism routes such as the tourist complex and ethnographic Park in the Ustyurt region of the Kondrat district, as well as the former Port of the Aral Sea in Furnak, international ecofestivals are organized

There are no less interesting aspects for sayohat lovers. On the territory of Karakalpakstan there is a historical and archaeological complex of Mizdakhan, Sultan Weiss Baba-sacred places, attractive for tourists. Today there are many myths and beliefs for popular tourist destinations. In this regard, the program of events is developing a new tourist route for travelers from neighboring Republics, infrastructure is being developed on the territory of tourist facilities.

References:

- 1.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Туризмни ривожлантириш Давлат кўмитаси Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси худудий бошқармаси 2017 – йиллик ҳисоботи. 3-б.
- 2.ЎЗР МДА М-7 фонд, 1-рўйхат, 1191-йиғма жилд, 7 вароқ
- 3.Вести Каракалпакстана. 2006. 15 май.
- 4.Gentleman A. «Savitsky's secret Hoard». The Guardian, January 1, 2001
- 5.S.Kinzer. In a Far Desert, a Startling Trove of Art // The New York Times. New York.: January 4, 1998.
- 6.J.Page. Oasis of the avant-garde" Australia// The Times September 1, 2004., Jeremy Page. Treasures hidden in the desert from Stalin// The Times London. September 1, 2004.
- 7.Рябкина Н. Золотой проект туризма //Вести Каракалпакстана. - 2002. - №71. - 3 сентября.
- 8.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий Мажлиснинг Ахборотномаси, 1999 й., 9-сон, 227-модда
- 9.Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами, 2016 й., 49-сон, 559-модда
- 10.Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси Вазирлар Кенгашининг Фармойиши, 2018 й. №194-Б., 3-б.
- 11.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Туризмни ривожлантириш Давлат кўмитаси Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси худудий бошқармаси 2018 – йиллик ҳисоботи. 1-б.
- 12.Вести Каракалпакстана. – 2006. – 26 июль
- 13.ҚР МДА 35 фонд, 3-рўйхат, 111-йиғма жилд, 199 вароқ
- 14.ҚР Маданият Вазирлиги ЖА. – 2017. – Б. 23.
- 15.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг «Ўзбекистон Республикаси туризм салоҳиятини ривожлантириш учун қулай шароитлар яратиш бўйича кўшимча ташкилий чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида» 2018 йил 3 февралдаги ПФ-5326-сон Фармони // <http://lex.uz/docs/3548467>
- 16.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг «Ички туризмни жадал ривожлантиришни таъминлаш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида» 2018 йил 7 февралдаги ПҚ-3514-сон Қарори // <http://lex.uz/docs/3551112>
- 17.И.Б.Жоллыбекова. Международное сотрудничество средних и высших специальных учебных заведений Каракалпакстана в научно-технической сфере и в подготовке кадров. Вестник развития науки и образования, 67-70, 2012

- 18.И.Жоллыбекова. Қорақалпоқ давлат университетининг халқаро алоқаларининг ривожланиши. Вестник Каракалпакского Государственного университета имени Бердаха №12014
- 19.Р.Дж.Уразбаева, И.Б.Жоллыбекова. Закон республики узбекистан" об образовании" и национальная программа по подготовке кадров: осуществление в системе высшего образования. Научная мысль, 34-36, 2015
- 20.И.Б. Жоллыбекова, Т.А. Абуллаев. Пути развития международного сотрудничества в области популяризации национального культурного наследия в годы независимости Республики Узбекистан. Научная мысль, 62-64, 2015
- 21.I.B. Jolibekova. Development of international cultural relations of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. International Journal on Integrated Education 2 (5), 105-108, 2019
- 22.Z.I.Bakhytovna.Foreign cooperation of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the field of environmental protection. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities 3, 58-60, 2021
- 23.IB Jolibekova. nternational Relations in the field of education in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.Science and Education in Karakalpakstan 2 (2), 93-99, 2018
- 24.ИБ Жоллыбекова.Вопросы оценки образования в современных условиях. атериалы международной научно-практической конференции 1 (2), 69-71, 2017